

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF PREVENTIVE MEASURES IN PREVENTING WOMEN AND GIRLS FROM BECOMING VICTIMS OF VIOLENCE AND CRIME IN SOCIETY.

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada muallif tomonidan Ichki ishlar organlari huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasi xizmati doirasida jamiyatda xotin-qizlarning profilaktik chora-tadbirlar orqali huquqbuzarliklardan jabrlanishini oldini olishning mazmun mohiyati ochib berilgan, ushbu yo'nalishda zarur va muhim profilaktika chora-tadbirlarining amalga oshirilishi dolzarb vazifa ekanligini asoslangan. Shuningdek, xotin-qizlarning huquqbuzarliklardan jabrlanishini oldini olishda kuzatilayotgan bir qancha muammolarga to'xtab o'tilib, xotin-qizlarning huquqbuzarliklardan jabrlanishi oqibatlarini nazariy va huquqiy tahlil qilingan hamda kerakli tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Tayanch tushunchalar: huquqbuzarlikdan jabrlanuvchi, tazyiq, zo'rvonlik, huquqbuzarliklarning viktimologik profilaktikasi, himoya ordeni, xotin-qizlarning huquqbuzarliklardan jabrlanishi sabablar hamda shart-sharoitlari

Аннотация. В данной статье автором раскрыта сущность предотвращения виктимизации женщин от преступлений в обществе путем профилактических мероприятий в рамках службы профилактики правонарушений органов внутренних дел, исходя из того, что осуществление необходимых и важных профилактических мероприятий в этом направлении является актуальной задачей. Также был обсужден ряд проблем, наблюдаемых в предотвращении виктимизации женщин от преступлений, теоретически и юридически проанализированы последствия виктимизации женщин от правонарушений, разработаны необходимые рекомендации.

Основные понятия: потерпевшие от преступлений, домогательства, насилие, виктимологическая профилактика преступлений, охранный ордер, причины и условия потерпевших женщин от преступлений.

Annotation. In this article, the author reveals the essence of preventing the victimization of women from crimes in society through preventive measures within the framework of the crime prevention service of the internal affairs bodies, based on the fact that the implementation of necessary and important preventive measures in this direction is an urgent task. A number of problems observed in the prevention of victimization of women from crimes were also discussed, the consequences of victimization of women from crimes were theoretically and legally analyzed, and the necessary recommendations were developed.

Keywords: victim of a crime, harassment, violence, victimological prevention of crimes, protection order, causes and conditions of women victims of crimes.

Today, in our country, women are a special category of victims of crimes. In recent years, the category of underage girls has been occupying the main place in the transformation of women into victims of crimes due to their victim nature. Currently, many measures are being implemented in the internal affairs bodies in order to ensure their social and legal protection

in order to prevent them from being victimized by violations, and normative legal documents on this urgent issue are being developed by the President and our supreme representative body. In particular, Decree No. 87 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further accelerate work on systematic support of families and women" adopted on March 7, 2022, Resolution PQ 5020 "On measures to further improve the system of supporting women and girls and ensuring their active participation in the life of society" adopted on March 5, 2021, PF Decree No. 81 on March 1, 2022 "On measures for systematic improvement of work with family and women, neighborhood and nurani support" and normative legal documents such as decision No.146 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the organization of the activities of the state committee for family and women" adopted on this date are a clear proof of this.

In addition, in order to ensure the employment of women, increase their legal literacy and further strengthen their social and legal protection, the President introduced several innovations in connection with the establishment of the State Committee for Family and Women. In particular, the development of the women's education support program for 2022-2026, the first 7-year interest-free loan to women to pay for education contracts from 2023, as well as, the need to support entrepreneurs who provide employment for needy women is assumed, and it can be shown that many tax and trade benefits will be introduced for them.¹ At the conference in connection with the establishment of the state committee for family and women, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev emphasized that both our current prosperous life and our bright future depend on women, "If we want our people to agree with us, first of all, we need to create decent living conditions for our respectable mothers and sisters. If the mother agrees, the family will agree, if the family agrees, the society will agree" shows the important place of women and girls in the society.²

Based on the above-mentioned reforms, special attention is being paid to strengthening the social legal protection of women and supporting them within the framework of the measures being implemented for the socio-economic development of the entire republic. Of course, in the implementation of these measures, the senior inspectors on women's issues, who are performing their duties in the Crime Prevention Service of the Internal Affairs bodies, have been making their due contribution. As a result of the implementation of work in each region of the republic in terms of district, neighborhood, street and citizens' home, once relevant information based on social life in each city, district, neighborhood, family and citizen has been gathered, targeted and meaningful measures are being set. In this regard, the inspectors of women's issues of the Internal Affairs bodies work closely with regional governors and self-governing bodies to eliminate the existing problems of women included in the "Iron Register", "Women's Register" and "Youth Register". Also, in order to protect the rights and interests of women who have been subjected to harassment and violence by them and are deemed to be in need of legal protection, on September 2, 2019, № LRU 651 "On the protection of women from harassment and abuse" the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted. Based on it, the "Protection Order" has been formalized, and the parties are given the

¹ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 1-mart kunidagi "Oila va xotin-qizlar davlat qo'mitasi faoliyatini tashkil etish to'g'risida"gi PQ-146 sonli qarori // <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-5884084>

² Prezident Shavkat Mirziyoyevning 1-mart kuni xotin-qizlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimi hamda ularning jamiyatdagi mavqegini yanada mustahkamlash masalalari bo'yicha videoselektordagi nutqi // Xalq so'zi 2022-yil 2-mart, № 45(1807) // <https://xs.uz>

results of the legal consequences of non-compliance with this document. The only goal of the implemented measures is to ensure the social and legal protection of women in our society and to prevent them from being victims of crimes while ensuring their employment.

In the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language, the word "Woman" is used in the meaning of a person of the opposite gender to a man, a wife, mainly in the plural form. This word has the meaning of generalization and means "Women and girls". The concept of "wife" means a person who is sexually contrary to the male category, who has the ability to have children and breastfeed, as well as a woman who is married to a man, and the concept of "girl" is explained in terms of a woman who has not reached the age of puberty, a child belonging to the female gender, a woman who has reached puberty but has not married to a man (innocent, virgin).

The concepts of woman and girl ensure that female persons differ not only in age, but also in biophysiological aspects, worldview, and life experience.

As one of the main concepts of the Law "On protection of women from harassment and violence", concepts such as harassment, violence, protection order have been defined. According to the law, harassment is an act (inaction) that degrades the honor and dignity of women, for which no administrative or criminal responsibility is provided, and violence is defined as physical, mental, their life, health, sexual integrity, honor, dignity and other rights protected by law by using sexual or economic influence or by threatening to use measures of such influence and an illegal action (inaction) that encroaches on their freedom is understood, and a protection order means a person or a group of persons who provide state protection to a victim of harassment and violence, harass women or commit violence against them, or a group of persons in this law it is emphasized that the document is understood as the reason for the application of specified impact measures. But no matter how many normative legal documents, laws and reforms are created on this issue, if we pay attention to last year's statistics, more than 15 thousand women suffered from harassment and violence, and because of this, more than 480 thousand women - it is possible to see that the girls are deceived, fall into the whirlpool of various frauds, and go to work abroad for a long time.

Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses" adopted on May 14, 2014 defines the concept of the victim of an offense as the main concept, and according to it, physical, property and it was mentioned that this definition will be given to a person who suffered from moral offenses. Article 6 of this law specifies victimological prevention as a special type of crime, and the articles 43-45 of Chapter 6 of the law are devoted to victimological prevention of crimes. In particular, Article 43 states that "the activity of a body or institution that directly implements the prevention of offenses in order to apply preventive measures aimed at reducing the risk of a specific person becoming a victim of an offense is victimological prevention of offenses" regular control of places (areas) where certain social behavior is observed relatively often or crimes are frequently committed, necessary defense in case of attack and last necessity information to the population by means of wide dissemination of legal information the measures of victimological prevention of offenses such as training and education, development and implementation of special complex measures aimed at ensuring the physical and psychological safety of the victim of offenses are defined.

Based on the above, the internal affairs bodies in the activities of prevention of crimes, preventive measures to prevent women from being victimized by crimes, in-depth study of

the theoretical and legal literature on this activity, researching it into practice, conducting scientific research in this field and widely promoting scientific research works not only requires implementation, but also requires all of these to be widely promoted by crime prevention officers as practical experience in the future.³

Many objective and subjective factors related to women become victims of crimes today. In particular, various reasons and conditions that enable the commission of this offense appear as a factor in their becoming victims of violations. In particular, the weakness of women compared to men, the revealing clothing of young girls, and their gullibility do not directly cause the offense, but they allow it to be committed. Their need for financial support, the burden of the family environment, and the corruption and immorality of their morals, in some sense, serve as a reason for women to suffer from violations.

If we analyze how women suffer from crimes in different ways, then in terms of percentages, it is more than crimes such as slander, insults, petty bullying, which are specified in the current Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan, suffering or becoming a victim of crimes against sexual freedom in the current Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a clear proof of this.

As a result of his experiences, the lawyer Q.A. Saitkulov included the following in the factors that indicate the possibility of victims of crimes and revealed the statistics of individual subjective victim characteristics (Fig. 1):⁴

Figure 1. Composition of factors that lead to victims of crimes⁵

Judging from these analyses, some problems in losing the victimological aspects of women in our society remain visible. Judging from these analyses, some problems in losing the victimological aspects of women in our society remain visible. Firstly, the fact that our women are not fully aware of their constitutional rights, freedoms and legal interests, and that legal literacy is not fully formed, secondly, the fact that inspectors and senior inspectors performing their duties in internal affairs bodies on women's issues do not cooperate with

³ Xo'Janazarova M. M. Xotin-qizlar o'rtasida huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasi samaradorligini oshirish dolzarb vazifa //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 6. – С. 170-175.

⁴ Сaitкулов Қ.А.. Ички ишлар органларининг хуқуқбузарликлар вѡкѡимологик профилактикаси бўйича фаолиятини такомиллаштириш: юрид. фан. б-ча фалсафа д-ри (PhD) дис.... автореф. – Т., 2020. – Б.17

⁵ Сaitкулов Қ.А.. Ички ишлар органларининг хуқуқбузарликлар вѡкѡимологик профилактикаси бўйича фаолиятини такомиллаштириш: юрид. фан. б-ча фалсафа д-ри (PhD) дис.... автореф. – Т., 2020. – Б.17

enterprises, institutions, organizations and other bodies to the required extent in order to prevent women from being victimized by crimes, thirdly, in coordination with preventive inspectors of women's activists of each neighborhood, in order to prevent women from being victimized by crimes, they should thoroughly study their social life and lifestyle, such as the fact that preventive measures are not being implemented in time is visible. Based on the problems in this area and the above-mentioned points, we can conclude that the internal affairs bodies in the crime prevention service, in preventing women from being victimized by crimes, such as inspectors on women's issues, in the territory of each community, Family and women in the state In working with women's issues, the women's activist operating in the lowest system of the committee, does not deal only with the women who have applied to the support point, but goes to the living rooms of all the women in their neighborhood and investigates their lifestyle and social life from house to house. In order to prevent them from suffering from violations, it is advisable to take the necessary preventive measures in time to solve their problems with preventive inspectors in this area. Also, in order to prevent women from becoming victims, in order to ensure their employment and meet their needs, in order to place them in work and provide social and legal assistance, they cooperate with enterprises, institutions, organizations, various social and legal assistance centers and other bodies in the regions. If we establish contacts and cooperation at various levels, and if we increase their legal awareness and legal culture by involving women in various cultural and educational events, we will prevent them from being victimized by violations at an early stage. if we ensure that other necessary preventive measures are implemented in time, it will allow us to positively prevent our women from being victims of crimes in our society.

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